

ORGANIZATION AND DEVELOPMENT MODELS OF THE PEDAGOGICAL PROCESS IN TEACHING ENGLISH**Babayeva Arzu Teyyub, teacher****Gunel Huseynli Zahir, teacher****Nasirova Hadiyya Firudin, teacher***College of Construction under AzMIU, Azerbaijan***Abstract**

The rapid changes taking place in the global educational space in modern times, technological progress and the requirements of the information society have made it necessary to reconsider the fundamental concepts of pedagogical science. Classical pedagogical concepts such as education, training and upbringing are no longer just a mechanism for transferring knowledge, but are perceived as dynamic processes aimed at the comprehensive development of the personality, its adaptation to the digital world and the disclosure of its creative potential. In this regard, an in-depth study of the essence of pedagogical concepts and the application of modern, innovative approaches to them are of strategic importance in the process of forming the younger generation. The reforms implemented in the education system, especially the introduction of new curriculum standards, require a redefinition of the roles of teachers and students. Now the learning process involves the student's transition from a passive listener to an active subject discovering knowledge. At the same time, the concept of upbringing is enriched with new shades such as digital ethics, critical thinking and global citizenship. Against the background of the rapid development of pedagogical technologies, the study of the regularities of personality development and formation comes to the fore as one of the most urgent issues in the field of education in Azerbaijan today. Since the development of human capital is a priority direction of state policy, the management of these processes on scientific and theoretical grounds is of particular relevance.

Keywords: teaching a foreign language, methods of teaching a foreign language, basic principles, features of use, goals

The transformation of pedagogical concepts is one of the most urgent intellectual needs of the modern era. Because education is not just a bridge that carries the experience of the past to the future, but also the main architectural tool that builds the future. Today, the terms "education", "training" and "upbringing" have transcended their classical boundaries and acquired a more global and digital nature. In an age of endless information flow, rather than giving students knowledge, the main goal of pedagogy has become to instill in them the ability to select, analyze and use that knowledge creatively. This, in turn, requires a completely new way of thinking from all participants in the pedagogical process - teachers, students and parents.

At the heart of modern pedagogical approaches is the idea of "human capital". The development of human capital is possible not only with high technological knowledge, but also with unshakable moral values. Therefore, along with the preservation of the national and spiritual heritage in the process of education, the synthesis of universal humanistic values takes a special place in the research object of the course work. New approaches present the pedagogical process not as a one-sided, but as an environment of mutual dialogue and cooperation. This approach allows for the establishment of differentiated education that takes into account the individual characteristics of students, their learning speed and psychological type. Thus, the understanding of pedagogical concepts in the modern context directly affects the improvement of education not only in terms of quantity, but also in terms of quality. It should also be noted that innovations in the science of pedagogy are based on the principles of humanization and democratization of education.

How to learn a language in teaching a foreign language has always been a subject of discussion. For this reason, many different methods have been developed and used. The methods used in teaching a foreign language have usually emerged to cover up the uselessness or shortcomings of a method used, and these efforts have contributed to better teaching of a foreign language. In order to effectively apply these methods in the teaching process, it is necessary to know the basic principles, goals, characteristics and shortcomings of the methods. The variety of methods available in teaching a foreign language is selected based on which language group the foreign language belongs to. Since each language has its own syntactic, morphological and phonetic characteristics, all languages to be taught as a foreign language must have their own teaching methods.

Language and literature have always been a unity. When writing articles or research works on language, bringing examples from fiction after explaining grammatical rules leads to a more complete development of the researched work. This idea can be applied to the teaching of grammatical material in the same way. If primitive examples are presented after explaining grammatical material during teaching, this causes the lesson to be dull. To express an idea, it is necessary to resort to facts.

Researchers who are engaged in the problem of forming communicative skills in students during training approach its solution from various aspects. Here, based on the results of the above analysis of the literature, it is more likely that in order to acquire English in communication, schools and teachers need to have an effective curriculum, a learning environment, and practical and competent teacher experience. It is explained

by the increased attention to the content, the application of interesting textbooks and materials, the distribution of necessary lesson hours, the planning of effective extracurricular activities, and the education of students in a healthy cultural environment. It is shown that the teaching of English within the framework of new educational programs (curricula) serves the new content that affects the formation of communicative skills, the effective organization of training and the correct measurement, that is, the evaluation of the acquired skills. Observations prove that the traditional method of applying reading and writing skills is still used in the teaching process. Although the methods based on many different theories and philosophical trends are presented in the foreign language subject curriculum in the form of a list, their origin is not clearly explained, and it is not explained which type of activity is used in the formation of communicative skills. Also, it is not explained why teachers should use these methods. The foreign language subject curriculum, as a state document, cannot be a teacher's daily program, since the standards and training strategies given for classes are of a general nature. The curricula for the grades are only general and undeveloped. Short (2-3 pages) sample curricula prepared for grades V-IX are compiled only on the basis of textbooks, and the provision of standards, topics, integration standards, resources and assessment tools does not explain the methodological side of the work to teachers.

In this regard, the communicative teaching of the English language subject in secondary schools within

the framework of the new curriculum is one of the problems that has not been sufficiently investigated. The specific fact that proves this is that although there are standards that form listening comprehension, speaking, reading and writing skills for teaching English from grade to grade in secondary schools, there is a need for a unified new school curriculum.

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